

Solar Sail Propelled CubeSat Autonomous Navigation in Deep Space: Experimental Asteroid Targeting With iPhone and DSLR Cameras

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Abstract

Solar sail missions in deep space are expected to require special navigational considerations due to relatively large stochastic disturbances over extremely long, very low-level thrusting time periods. This paper presents early experimental results on beacon asteroid detection — part of an undergraduate thesis project on realistic autonomous optical navigation simulations of small spacecraft propelled to Mars by a solar sail. Such a mission offers additional technological challenges, given the mass and volume limitations upon the design of the imaging subsystem, which affect the maximum magnitude of beacon asteroids detectable at very long range. Here we discuss observations carried out with an iPhone 11 camera and a Nikon D3100 DSLR camera, both on a tripod and operated in parked mode, without equatorial tracking. The workflow was adapted from that used in our university classwork and designed for asteroid orbit calculation by means of commercial digital cameras, appropriately modified to solve the classical inverse problem of the determination of the position of the observer. A discussion will be presented of the centroid coordinate observational errors for both imaging systems and of error propagation to the spacecraft dynamical state estimates. This analysis will yield a first estimate of the mass penalty corresponding to a required gain in the detectable asteroid apparent magnitude. A software data pipeline from onboard data acquisition to the final spacecraft navigational solution will be presented. Next steps in the implementation of the approach discussed in this thesis in an operational environment shall be considered.

1. Introduction

Nowadays deep space missions are the most improving section in the space industry. Interplanetary missions and asteroid mining are two of example for deep space missions. Propulsion motors is not efficient and not usable regarding the needed fuel amount. Regarding communications and navigation, particular challenges apply throughout the mission. The distance of the spacecraft from the ground stations may be problematic due to time. In this conference paper, the optical navigation subsystem of a mission targeting Mars and its Moons will be considered (Zengin et al. 2023). With this approach, beacon asteroids and comets are used for calculating the position of the spacecraft. The main focus of this paper will be asteroid and comet detection with an iPhone (Odenwald 2023) and a Nikon D3100 DSLR camera. For asteroid and comet targeting and detection, the decision was made to only make use of Free Open Source Software (FOSS) and other tools licensed as freeware although, possibly, not yet open sourced (Pinto 2022).

2. Methodology

2.1 Observation Planning

The first step in observation planning is knowledge of available equipment and geographical location. As far as equipment, a critical piece of information for observation planning is the maximum apparent magnitude reachable. To determine such maximum magnitude, observations must be made to detect relatively faint whose magnitude is known from existing catalogs. With that knowledge, it can be assumed that celestial objects with lower magnitudes (i.e. brighter) than that maximum value, can be detected in the image. In this project, data are obtained from the website *theskylive.com* and the FOSS planetarium program *Stellarium*, combined with data from observations.

2.2 Observations

During the observations, attempts were made to minimize both the human and environmental effects on the equipment. To stabilize the camera, a tripod was used and during image acquisition, the camera was

connected to a computer, via the app 'digiCamControl'. By this procedure, pictures were taken without any physical human intervention. By these methods, vibrations can be prevented, and the correct timing can be achieved by synchronizing both the camera and the computer have synchronized with atomic clock time provided by the time.is app.

Figure 1 Observation setup example. (DSLR Camera)

Figure 2 Observation setup example with the author. (iPhone Camera)

Image calibration for all acquired images is of course necessary. Without calibration, dust, for example, may affect the results as also uncontrolled temperature of the sensor. (see Sec. 2.3).

Figure 3 Flat frame setup example. (DSLR Camera)

2.3 Data Processing

In this Section, we consider the workflow leading from raw, uncalibrated light images to the final science frame by using calibration frames.

2.3.1. Dark Frames

The camera pixels gather a signal proportional to the exposure duration even in the absence of light (Armin 1996). The random flow of electrons within the semiconductor is the cause of this dark or thermal count. The dark pixel reading needs to be determined in order to accurately calibrate a raw image accurately.

Temperature has an impact on dark frames in addition to exposure. As a result, the dark frames need to be taken at the same temperature as the light images.

The requirements are as follows: the dark exposure must match the exposure of the image, the camera lens must be fully dark and covered, and the dark frames must be taken at the same temperature as the light images.

2.3.2. Flat Frames.

The flat frame is a map of the relative sensitivity of each detector pixel, whereas the flat calibration accounts for variations in the camera sensitivity and aberrations in the telescope field of view. These frames are produced by imaging a surface that is uniformly lit.

Because of the very short exposures involved, temperature has no appreciable bearing on flat frames. Thus, the flat calibrations are relatively portable.

The entire area in front of the camera must be uniformly illuminated; this can be a full white screen, full white paper, etc. (Armin 1996).

2.3.3. Bias Frames.

The bias frame is an error caused by camera charge. When the camera gets active a signal has starts, therefore there might be an error in this signal.

Bias also affected by temperature too. The temperature of the surroundings and the temperature of the sensors effects the charge of the camera.

For taking bias, camera lenses need to be closed and then the shortest exposure must have been selected, then the bias can be taken.

2.3.4. Light Frames.

Light frames are the raw images themselves, that is, the actual images of celestial objects.

In this paper, 50 images were taken for each of them. The exposure for both light and dark frames is 1 second. The ISO value of the camera is 12800, although, under particular circumstances, the ISO was chosen as 6400. All raw light images are stacked after calibration (Armin 1996).

2.3.5. Stacking Process by DeepSkyStacker (DSS)

Astro photographers all around the world use DeepSkyStacker, a well-liked and effective stacking tool, which is free and accessible in 12 languages (Ashley 2015).

It is a free and open-source tool for stacking astronomical photos in relation to calibration frames and star rotation. As stated in previous sections, frames are used in the calibration procedure.

When the stacking process is completed, DSS automatically saves a “.tif” file, also if wanted the stacking process's info can be saved as a “.txt” file. For the data process the “.fits” file is needed. So, in this paper, GIMP was used for changing the “.tif” file to the “.fits” file. Here is in the figure 4 output of DSS can be seen as an example.

Figure 4 DSS output.

2.3.6. Astrometry.net

The algorithm accessible at this website carries out astrometric image calibrations. Following the calibration and stacking in DSS, images are sent to Astrometry.net for plate solving. That method allows one to determine the precise position of the photo as well as its celestial coordinates in the sky. The details of the “blind calibration approach” are clarified by Lang (Lang et al. 2010), where further details are found.

Figure 5 Astrometry.net output.

As can be seen from figure 5 *astrometry.net* provides a reliable calibration and also marks important celestial objects and it calculates the center Right Ascension (RA) and Declination (Dec) values of the image, so that way position calculation of any object can be carried out.

Figure 6 Astrometry.net output for a particular cropped area.

2.3.7. Astrometric Stacking Program (ASTAP)

One Free Open-Source Software tool that can stack images and determine RA-Dec values is called ASTAP (Astrometric Stacking Program). ASTAP was utilized in this research project to obtain the RA-Dec values of the objects. Astrometry.net performed the astrometric calibration computations prior to ASTAP, such as determining the image center as RA-Dec values. That calibration allows ASTAP to compute the RA-Dec of each pixel. In this paper, ASTAP was used to obtain the celestial coordinates of asteroids and comets. ASTAP also aids in locating asteroids and comets when the observation date is included in the fits header.

Figure 7 ASTAP Output for a particular cropped area with marked asteroids.

As can be seen from figure 7, one of the main objects of this paper is represented by the objects at the center of the square provided by ASTAP.

The overall workflow executed for this paper is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8 Workflow (Sketched via diagrams.net).

In the last part of the workflow, a comparison with the data that comes from pictures and the data that comes from *Stellarium* (data based on NASA JPL) has been made. This is the part that is going to be used in the optical navigation part as the next step. The aim is to make the optical navigation calibrations and prove that.

3. Results

In this paper, 2 celestial objects were studied, the asteroid (4) Vesta and the comet 12P/Pons-Brooks. These objects are going to be used in simulated optical navigation as beacon celestial objects.

3.1 Vesta Detection with an iPhone 11's Camera

While these observations were made, Vesta had a magnitude approximately equal to +6 thus, being visible even with a smartphone camera.

For a CubeSat mission, a small camera is necessary due to the small surface area mass required. For that reason, detecting an asteroid with a smartphone camera is a capstone for a CubeSat mission that is going to use optical navigation.

Figure 9 Final image (iPhone Camera).

Figure 9 is an output image from astrometry.net astrometric calibration. As can be seen, there is a square in a particular area. Vesta is located at the center of the red rectangle.

Figure 10 Red rectangle area in the previous image. (iPhone Camera).

As the next step concerning that scientific final image, the position calculation of Vesta is going to be made, and then again respect to that position the CubeSat's position is going to be calculated.

Expected Coordinates:
 6h 02m 43.25s,
 +20° 25' 02.2''

Measured Coordinates:
 6h 19m 26.88s,
 +20° 55' 19.1''

3.2 Vesta Detection with a Nikon D3100 DSLR Camera

While the observations with the DSLR camera were made, Vesta had a magnitude around +8, which is beyond the iPhone 11's detection limit. A zoomed area around Vesta is shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 11 Zoomed image of figure 5. (DSLR Camera).

The same process is going to be applied in this image.

Expected Coordinates:
 6h 12m 43.37s,
 +24° 45' 19.0''

Measured Coordinates:
 6h 12m 03.03s,
 +24° 44' 27.9''

3.3 Comet 12P/Pons-Brooks Detection with a Nikon D3100 DSLR Camera

While the observations were made, comet 12P/Pons-Brooks had a magnitude of around +4 making even the tail of the comet visible in the final science frame (figs. 12-13).

Figure 12 Final image for 12P/Pons-Brooks. (DSLR Camera).

Figure 13 Squared area that zoomed. (DSLR Camera).

The same calibration workflow described previously is applied in this image to investigate the possibility to use comets as well as optical navigation beacons.

Expected Coordinates:

2h 49m 28.62s,
+16° 57' 41.7''

Measured Coordinates:

2h 49m 39.46s,
+17° 02' 24.5''

4. Conclusions

Following the workflow we discussed, science frames were produced. These images show beacon celestial objects to carry out optical navigation for a CubeSat mission. In this paper, we demonstrated the remote detection of two such beacon celestial objects by means of a phone camera and a small DSLR camera. These experimental results, in agreement with the expected ephemeris positions, show that a small camera can be used for autonomous optical navigation in deep space missions.

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